

INFLUENCE OF MILL GEOMETRY ON CUTTING FORCE AND SURFACE MORPHOLOGY OF MULTIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

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1 Introduction

With the development of fabrication of advanced materials, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been used extensively in many industries due to their superior specific strength and high temperature resistance, high corrosion resistance and good thermal shock resistance [1-3]. Especially in the aircraft industry, CFRP could reduce fuel consumption for economic and environmental reasons as lightweight and high-strength materials while maintain safety standards and durability. So their usage in new generation of aircrafts has been steadily increasing while Airbus A380 has been 22% and Boeing B787 has been 50% [4]. The large passenger aircraft programs in China are being implemented and CFRP on the C919 (Chinese trunk liner) account for 20% of the aircraft's structural weight [5]. Although CFRP are usually near net shaped, most of the CFRP parts need to be trimmed to satisfy the finished dimensions because the layered sheets have a peripheral margin. In order to produce a well defined and high quality surface, milling is the most practical machining operation for removing excess material. However, machining of CFRP comes along with certain difficulties like fiber pull-out, delamination and decomposition of matrix material due to the inhomogeneous and anisotropic material properties which leads to a degradation of the surface quality and the material properties [6]. Furthermore, the rapid tool wear is commonly observed due to the abrasive nature of carbon fibers. So the main challenges are low quality and high tool wear during milling CFRP.

Research on milling CFRP has been on-going for over 20 years, but the number of paper published on milling of CFRP laminates is quite limited. Hocheng et al. showed that there was a relationship between the cutting mechanisms and resulting surface roughness when milling unidirectional CFRP

[7]. Sheikh-Ahmad [8] and Kalla et al. [9] utilized mechanistic modeling techniques for simulating the cutting of CFRP. Hintze et al. [10] studied the occurrence and propagation of delamination by milling slots in unidirectional CFRP. They concluded that delamination was highly dependent on the fiber orientation and the tool sharpness. Karpat et al. [11] proposed a mechanistic cutting force model for milling CFRP based on experimentally collected cutting force data during slot milling of unidirectional CFRP laminates. Schulze et al. [12] calculated experimentally specific cutting forces, passive and axial forces on glass fiber reinforced plastics for varied parameters of cutting velocity, cutting depth, cutting edge rounding and tool inclination. Ramulu et al. recommended that 3D roughness parameters were preferable for characterizing machined CFRP surfaces to 2D roughness parameters [13]. Furthermore, they suggested that assessment of several parameters were necessary in order to provide a comprehensive description of a surface [14]. And previous studies have also found that high cutting speeds in tandem with low feed rates generally resulted in improved surface quality when edge milling due to the lower amount of mechanical/thermal damage induced [15, 16].

To solve the problem of rapid tool wear, diamond coated carbide tools and PCD tools are usually employed for milling CFRP. For the low quality problem, a large number of studies suggest that delamination is the most important quality problem and axial force tend to separate the top and bottom layers of the CFRP laminate. And delamination is strongly dependent on the tool geometry. To minimize axial forces, milling tools with special designs have been proposed such as double helix mill and multi-edge mill. Double helix mill could minimize axial forces by utilizing two opposite helix angles so that top and bottom layers

of the laminate are pushed inwards to decrease the likelihood of delamination [17]. Similarly, the multi-edge mill has also been considered as a better option, because no axial force component is produced [18].

In the present study, down milling processes of multidirectional CFRP with double helix tools and multi-edge mill are investigated. The objectives of this research are to find relationships among the mill geometry, cutting force and surface morphology of the workpieces. To identify potential damages at the machined surface, cross-sectional micrographs of the specimen are analyzed. And the cross-sectional roughness has been measured.

2 Experimental procedures

The CFRP laminates are fabricated from IMS/X850 prepregs with T800 carbon fibers. The lay-up of the multidirectional CFRP composites laminates is $[(45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ)_6]_s$ and the fiber volume fraction is 65%. Each laminate has 48 plies, so CFRP laminates have a thickness of 9mm. The laminates are cut into $200\text{mm} \times 150\text{mm}$ using diamond-edged saw to fit the clamp.

All milling experiments have been carried out on a DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear as shown in Fig. 1(a). The DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear has maximum spindle speed of 42 000rpm and maximum feed speed of 5 m/min. The experimental data are collected with a data acquisition system composed of a 9272 Kistler drilling dynamometer and a 5070A Kistler amplifier. The fixation of the composite material laminate is made as shown in Fig. 1(b), to make sure that vibrations and displacement are eliminated. The CVD diamond coated end-mills have been employed to avoid the effect of tool wear on the cutting force, surface morphology and roughness. The multi-edge mill and double helix mill are employed as shown in Fig.1(c) and (d) whose diameters D both are 10mm. In order to minimize axial forces, the two opposite helix angles of double helix mill are arranged symmetrically with respect to the middle plane of the CFRP laminates as shown in Fig.2. The milling forces acting on the tool during milling CFRP laminates are also illustrated in Fig.2.

The experimental planning is prepared by using cutting parameters and test conditions that are advised for a couple of tool-workpiece by the tool manufacturer. A multivariate factor method for two

factors (cutting speed v_c and feed speed f) is used for the elaboration of the plan of experiments.

(a) The experimental equipments

(b) Fixation of the composite material

(c) Multi-edge mill (d) Double helix mill

Fig. 1. The experimental equipments and the geometries of milling tools

Table 1 indicates the factors studied which is made of 12 tests with four factors. The cutting radial depth a_e is 1 mm and the cutting axial depth a_p is 9

mm that is just equal to the laminates thickness. The test of different parameter combinations have been replicated five times.

Fig. 2 Arrangement of double helix mill and milling forces acting on the tool during milling

After milling, the cross-sectional roughness has been measured by a roughness measure instrument Perthometer M1 and for each test 5 measurements are made over milling surfaces. Then, the surface quality has also been observed through scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Cutting Force

The analysis of cutting forces during such an operation is helpful for understanding causes of possible damage. The recorded cutting forces in x-, y-, and z-directions are plotted on the same graph as shown in Fig. 3. The directions of forces F_x , F_y and F_z are along the normal, feed and axial directions, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2. Signals of the cutting forces obtained with multi-edge mill are shown in Fig. 3(a) and that with double helix mill are shown in Fig. 3(b) during milling of the multidirectional laminates, respectively. Fig. 3 sorts out the similarity of the cutting forces F_y and F_z for the two mills. Compared to milling forces in x-(F_x)

directions, milling forces in y- (F_y) and z-direction (F_z) are very small. The small value of F_y can be attributed to the small radial depth of cut. Since the double helix mill and laminate midpoints are aligned, the milling forces F_z are offset by two opposite helix angles. The small value of F_z for the multi-edge mill could be attributed to the flexible components of the multitooth which eliminates the cutting force along the Z-axis.

Due to the difference of the cutting forces F_x between double helix mill and multi-edge mill, the cutting force F_x are mainly discussed in this paper. Because of the signal variations during mill rotation, the values of cutting forces F_x are averaged and also to reduce the influence of outlier values, the final results used are the average of five experiments run under identical conditions. The trend of the change in the cutting force F_x with the mill geometry, cutting speed and feed speed is illustrated in Fig.4. The cutting force F_x is mainly affected by cutting tool geometry and parameters. Tool geometry has an important effect on the cutting force F_x . At any feed speed and cutting speed, the obtained mean cutting force F_x value with the multi-edge mill is found to be much lower than those of that with the double helix mill. Minimum mean cutting force value is obtained as 57.1N at feed speed $f=150\text{mm/min}$ and cutting speed $v_c=157.1\text{m/min}$, and maximum mean cutting force value is found to be 141.2N at feed speed $f=450\text{mm/min}$ and cutting speed $v_c=94.2\text{m/min}$ with the multi-edge mill. However, minimum mean cutting force value is obtained as 171.1N at feed speed $f=150\text{mm/min}$ and cutting speed $v_c=157.1\text{m/min}$, and maximum mean cutting force value is found to be 251.2N at feed speed $f=450\text{mm/min}$ and cutting speed $v_c=94.2\text{m/min}$ with the double helix mill. The main reason is that can be connected to the tool edge length. The double-helix mill has continuous cutting edges which results in a larger cutting area, but the multi-edge mill has intermittent cutting edges.

A clear trend has been found regarding the effect of feed speed and cutting speed independently of tool geometry as same as most researches. It has been observed that when the cutting speed increase and feed speed decrease, all cutting forces F_x are reduced of two tools as shown in Fig. 4. High temperature at flow region and decreasing contact surface area cause the cutting force to decrease in comparison to the increased cutting speed.

Table 1 Cutting parameters for force tests

N (rpm)	v_c (m/min)	f (mm/min)	a_p (mm)	a_e (mm)	D (mm)
3000	94.2	150	9	1	10
3000	94.2	250	9	1	10
3000	94.2	350	9	1	10
3000	94.2	450	9	1	10
4000	125.6	150	9	1	10
4000	125.6	250	9	1	10
4000	125.6	350	9	1	10
4000	125.6	450	9	1	10
5000	157.1	150	9	1	10
5000	157.1	250	9	1	10
5000	157.1	350	9	1	10
5000	157.1	450	9	1	10

(a) Cutting force signals with multi-edge mill

(b) Cutting force signals with double helix mill

Fig. 3. Typical cutting force signals ($v_c = 125.6$ m/min, $f = 250$ mm/min)

Fig. 4. Cutting force Fx

Meanwhile, with the increase of feed rate, the contact area between tool and workpiece increases. As a result, material removal rate increases which contribute to the increase in cutting forces.

3.2 Surface morphology

The change of surface morphology has hardly been influenced by the cutting speed at the certain feed speed. So, only at the cutting speed $v_c=125.6$ m/min, the change of surface morphology are illustrated in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 with the feed speed and the varied mills, respectively. The changes of surface morphology can be affected by fiber orientation, tool geometry and feed speed.

The surface morphology mainly relates to the fiber orientation as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. Plies oriented at 45° suffered severe damage where fibers are generally bent and lifted-up as the cutting edge advanced, which can subsequently cause splitting or interfacial failure of fiber bundles and the matrix. Some of these fibers then proceeded to fracture/were pulled out while others were merely flexed, thereby producing a wavy surface. Surfaces with fibers at 0° generally showed the least damage, with fibers removed cleanly as a result of fracture by buckling [19]. Fiber pull out was observed in 90° and -45°

plies leading to empty holes or large grooves as fibers tended to break at locations beneath the machined surface/depth of cut [20]. The softened matrix allows flexible fibers to escape from the cutting edge and spread over a wider area, especially those in the 90° and -45° direction.

At the same time, the toll geometry has played an important role in the change of surface morphology. The surface machined with double helix mill is smoother than that machined with multi-edge mill. The main reason is that the continuous cutting edges of double-helix mill result in more serious friction between the workpiece and the tool flank surface than the intermittent cutting edges of the multi-edge mill do. Furthermore, with the increase of feed speed the surface morphology has changed. The matrix has hardly changed. However, plies oriented at varied fiber orientation have changed nonuniformly. With the increase of feed speed, plies oriented at 45° have changed significantly and plies oriented at 90° have also changed. But plies oriented at 0° and -45° have changed very little. Increasing feed speed leads to higher cutting forces. Then the stresses increase which results in the more severe damage to carbon fiber, especially in plies oriented at 45° .

(a) $v_c = 125.6 \text{ m/min}$, $f = 150 \text{ mm/min}$

(a) $v_c = 125.6 \text{ m/min}$, $f = 150 \text{ mm/min}$

(b) $v_c = 125.6 \text{ m/min}$, $f = 250 \text{ mm/min}$

(b) $v_c = 125.6 \text{ m/min}$, $f = 250 \text{ mm/min}$

(c) $v_c = 125.6 \text{ m/min}$, $f = 450 \text{ mm/min}$

Fig. 5. Micrographs with double helix mill

(c) $v_c = 125.6 \text{ m/min}$, $f = 450 \text{ mm/min}$

Fig. 6. Micrographs with multi-edge mill

3.3 Roughness Measurement

The recorded roughness is plotted as shown in Fig. 7. The average surface roughness Ra is measured within the sampling length of 5.6 mm. It means that includes about 30 plies and 7 or 8 plies oriented at 45° result in the peaks. The measured roughness Ra results of milling surface with varied tools are shown in Table 2 at varied cutting speed and feed speed which the final results are the average of five experiments run under identical conditions.

Fig. 7. Micrographs of specimens

The measured cross-sectional roughness results show the roughness value used double helix mill is smaller than that used multi-edge router. This is similar to the observed results of surface morphology. In spite of the effect of the mill geometry, it is clear from these figures that the

surface roughness falls with the increase of cutting speed; however, it increases with the increase of feed speed. i.e. to get a better surface finishing it is necessary a high cutting speed and a low feed speed.

From Table 2 it can be inferred that the value of Ra increases with the feed rate, and decreases with the cutting speed, i.e. to get a better surface finishing it is necessary a high cutting speed and a low feed rate. The main reason is that the surface morphology becomes rough when the feed speed f increases. However, at the present experiments, the roughness Ra with the multi-edge mill bigger than the $3.2\mu\text{m}$ that has been typically required for aerospace applications [21]. So, the smaller feed speed should be required to improve the surface quality.

Table 2 the roughness Ra of through-hole inner wall

v_c (m/min)	f (mm/min)	Ra (μm)	
		Multi-edge mill	Double helix mill
94.2 (3000rpm)	150	3.03	2.28
	250	3.36	2.32
	350	3.41	2.39
	450	3.49	2.76
125.6 (4000rpm)	150	3.55	2.20
	250	3.96	2.43
	350	4.53	2.59
	450	4.85	2.71
157.1 (5000rpm)	150	4.48	2.14
	250	5.35	2.21
	350	5.43	2.47
	450	5.65	2.66

4 Conclusions

Based on the experimental results obtained from the cutting force and machining quality after milling multidirectional CFRP, the following conclusions can be extracted.

- (1) The cutting force mainly relates to the geometry of tools and increases with the increase of feed speed and the decrease of cutting speed.
- (2) At the same cutting parameters, the surface morphology varied with the mill geometry. The surface machined with double helix mill is smoother than that machined with multi-edge mill. However, the surface morphology has changed nonuniformly which depends on the orientation of carbon fiber with the increase of feed speed.

- (3) The measured cross-sectional roughness results show the roughness value used double helix mill is smaller than that used multi-edge mill. This is similar to the observed results of surface morphology. In spite of the effect of the mill geometry, the roughness value of Ra increases with the feed rate, and decreases with the cutting speed.

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